

SUSAAN

SUSTainable **A**ntimicrobial
and **A**ntiviral **N**anocoating

New Sustainable Antiviral and Antimicrobial Nanocoating for textile, plastic and metallic high traffic objects, developing Active Nano Materials (ANMs) to improve efficiency, decreasing contact time and toxicity.

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PROJECT DETAILS

Start Date: 01 June 2022

Duration: 42 months

SUSAAN project aims to develop antiviral and antimicrobial surfaces including development of fast active response and durable surfaces, considering ease of use, low toxicity and health issues and finally targeting a global sustainability concept, understood as environmental, economic and social sustainability for the required product and application.

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

- Developing a range of improved Active Nano Materials (ANMs) safely- tailored to the applications.
- Increasing fast performance and durability of the AM/AV coatings on high-traffic non-porous surfaces.
- Increasing sustainability and stability of the AM/AV coatings on textiles.
- Validating the scalability of the products and the pathways for commercialization.

PROJECT PARTNERS

